

over crushed ice. The solid obtained was washed with sodium hydroxide (2%) to remove uncyclised oxime, filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

Scheme 3

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (C. H. G.) is thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. C. K. GHOSH and S. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **18**, 128.
2. A. NOHARA, T. UMETANI and Y. SANNO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1973, 1995.
3. A. NOHARA, T. UMETANI and Y. SANNO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 3553.
4. A. NOHARA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 1187.
5. A. NOHARA, T. ISHIGURO and Y. SANNO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 1189.
6. A. H. BLATT and L. A. RUSSEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1903.
7. K. A. THAKAR, D. D. GOSWAMI and B. M. BHAWAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **15**, 1058.
8. E. P. KOHLER and W. F. BRUCE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 1569.
9. K. V. AUWERS, *Chem. Abst.*, 1925, **19**, 1401.
10. M. R. CHANDRANOHAN and S. SHESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 573.

[1,3,4]Thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines

H. K. GAKHAR*, USHA PRABHA and J. K. GILL

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University,
Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 15 September 1983, accepted 9 March 1984

ALTHOUGH a number of [1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines are known¹⁻⁴, no attempt seems to have been made so far for the synthesis of their 2,3-dihydro derivatives. We report here the syntheses of some 5-oxo-2,3-dihydro-5H-[1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines with substitutions in positions 2 and 6. These have been prepared by the condensation of 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-substituted-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazines (I) with various aldehydes. Structure III for these compounds finds support from analytical results, ir and pmr data. IR of IIIa

gave a band at 1670 due to amide while the NH band appeared at 3170 cm⁻¹. PMR of IIIa in DMSO-d₆ (chemical shifts in δ ppm) showed a sharp singlet (3H) at 2.3, assignable to three protons

of methyl group at C-6 (CH₃-C(=O)-). The five aromatic protons and one benzylic proton at C-2 merged to give a multiplet (6H) at 7.50-8.50. The structure IIIa finds further support from its insolubility in dil. sodium hydroxide solution.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in paraffin bath and are uncorrected. IR spectrum was recorded in nujol on Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr on Varian EM 390 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel plates.

4-Amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-substituted-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazines (I): These were prepared starting from thiocarbohydrazide⁵ and pyruvic acid or benzoylformic acid according to the procedure of Dornow *et al.*⁶

6-Methyl-2-phenyl-5-oxo-2,3-dihydro-5H[1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines (IIIa): Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through a chilled ethereal suspension (20 ml) of 4-amino-6-methyl-5-oxo-3-thioxo-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (Ia, R = CH₃; 1.58 g, 0.01 mol) till it was saturated. After decanting off the ethereal layer, the solid mass was suspended in absolute ethanol (40 ml). To this was added benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) and the contents refluxed on steam bath under nitrogen atmosphere (by continuous bubbling of dry nitrogen). As the reaction progressed the suspension dissolved with simultaneous separation of a new solid. Progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc at regular intervals. It was refluxed for 4 h in all. After concentration, it was cooled and the solid product was collected under suction, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. Other aldehydes were also condensed with Ia under similar conditions.

4-Amino-5-oxo-6-phenyl-3-thioxo-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (Ib) was also condensed with

a, R = CH₃
b, R = C₆H₅

various aldehydes. The data regarding the m.p. and yield of these compounds are tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I—5-Oxo-2,6-disubstituted-2,3-dihydro-5H-[1,3,4]thiadiazolo[2,3-c][1,2,4]triazines

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	yield %
a	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	203	40
b	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (3')	238	47
c	CH ₃	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₄ (3',4')	233	45
d	CH ₃	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₃ NO ₂ (3',4',6')	228	50
e	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	232	55
f	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (3')	228	59
g	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₄ (3',4')	225	58
h	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ O, C ₆ H ₃ NO ₂ (3',4',6')	250	51
i	C ₆ H ₅	HO, C ₆ H ₄ OOH ₂ (5',3')	236	52

All these compounds were crystallised from ethanol and gave satisfactory analysis for C, H and N.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. L. Lakhnarpal, Chairman, Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh for providing the research facilities and Mr. Avtar Singh for pmr spectrum of the compounds.

References

1. A. DORNOW and P. MARX, *Ber.*, 1964, **97**, 2640.
2. Z. KAROLY, P. JOZSEF, N. JOZSEF, H. GYULA, W. ANDRAS, D. GABOV and L. KAROLY, *Period Polytech. Chem. Eng.*, 1968, **12**, 259.
3. H. GOLGOLAB, I. LALEZARI and L. H. GOHARI, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1973, **10**, 887.
4. A. SHAFIAE, I. LALEZARI and M. MIRRAHED, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 117.
5. L. F. ANDRIETH, E. S. SCOTT and P. S. KIPPUR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 739.
6. A. DORNOW, H. MENZEL and P. MARX, *Ber.*, 1964, **97**, 2178.

Reaction of Homophthalic Acid with *m*-Hydroxybenzoic Acid

B. K. SARKHEL, (Mrs.) A. GHOSH

and

JAGADISH N. SRIVASTAVA*

Department of Chemistry, Bhaagalpur University,
Bhaagalpur-812 007

Manuscript received 6 February 1982, revised 8 October 1982,
accepted 23 April 1983

In general, 3-phenylisocoumarins¹⁻⁴ have been synthesised by direct condensation of homophthalic anhydride with aromatic hydrocarbon, phenols, phenolic ether, etc. using anhyd. AlCl₃ or stannous chloride as a condensing agent. It was later found that polyphosphoric acid was a good cyclodehydrating agent⁴ for the synthesis of 3-phenyl isocoumarins.

In continuation of our previous work⁵⁻⁸, we report here the condensation of homophthalic acid (I) with 3-hydroxybenzoic acid (IIb) in presence of polyphosphoric acid to furnish 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-isocoumarin (III) followed by a neutral compound and 6'-hydroxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno

(2',3' : 3,4)-isocoumarin (IV). III on either refluxing with phosphorus oxychloride in dry benzene or heating with polyphosphoric acid yielded IV. Solution of IV in acetone on methylation with methyl iodide in presence of potassium carbonate gave 6'-methoxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno-(2',3' : 3,4)-isocoumarin.

Experimental

6'-Hydroxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno (2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarin: A mixture of homophthalic acid (3.6 g), *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid (3.0 g) and commercial polyphosphoric acid (15 g) was taken in a hard glass test tube, fitted with anhydrous calcium chloride tube and heated at 140-45° for 1.5 h in a glycerol bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice and left for a few h. The precipitate that separated was filtered and washed well with water. The crude product was triturated with aqueous sodium carbonate and allowed to stand for a few h. The solid product was filtered, washed well with water and crystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless crystals, m.p. 249-50°, (0.8 g) (Found : C, 72.73; H, 2.98. Calcd. for C₁₆H₈O₅; C, 72.71; H, 3.07%). IR : 2850, 1715, 1702, 1610 cm⁻¹. NMR (CDCl₃) : 7.2-7.8 (m, 6H, aromatic); 8.3 (m, 1H, C-8, peri-aromatic proton) and 10.0 (s, 1H, -OH).

3-(2'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl)isocoumarin (III): The aqueous sodium carbonate filtrate obtained during the preparation of IV on acidification yielded a mixture of 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl) isocoumarin, unreacted homophthalic acid and *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid. The mixture obtained was treated with hot water when homophthalic acid and *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid dissolved, whereas 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl) isocoumarin remained undissolved. It was filtered hot and crystallised as colourless crystals, m.p. 182-88° (1.2 g) (Found : C, 68.01; H, 3.49. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀O₅; C, 68.08; H, 3.54%). IR : 2680, 1720, 1695, 1650 cm⁻¹.

Cyclodehydration of III to 6'-hydroxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno (2',3' : 3,4) isocoumarin (IV):

Method I: III (0.5 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed with phosphorous oxychloride (3.5 ml) on a water bath for 4.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the benzene layer was washed